

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

OPEN EDUCATION AS A PHENOMENON OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the foundation of essential characteristics and the definition of tendencies of Open Education innovative development in Ukraine. To realize the outlined goal a description of the main factors of its development will be produced as well as the specification of the current tasks and developing tendencies of Open Education in Ukraine.

Keywords: Open Education, digitalization, the educational and political aspects, innovative development, democratization.

Open Education is a complex social phenomenon, the study of which involves a holistic study, systematization and classification of sources in numerous sciences, which have formed a developed multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary discourse in recent decades. The most developed components of the discourse include research in the field of sociology of education, educational policy, pedagogical innovation, etc. The complex nature of the investigated concept involves a systematic consideration of external and internal factors of its development, educational and political processes and regulatory documents, goals, objectives, principles, functions, content, forms, methods, means, technologies, results, criteria and quality assessment procedures, etc. Having studied all the diversity of scientific investigations of domestic authors we singled out the most important aspect of consideration, the educational and political one.

The educational and political aspect of Open Education is represented in the studies of such Ukrainian scientists as Bykov (2005; 2010), Geits (2015), Danylenko and Libanova (2004), Kremen (2016), Lugovoi (2008), Shunevich (2008) etc.

In particular, the leading Ukrainian expert in the field of educational digitalization, Bykov (2010), singles out a wide range of factors of successful development of Open Education:

- democratization of the process of obtaining education, in particular, open choice and equal access to high-quality education of the general population, without consideration of their social status, place of residence, physical or mental capabilities;
- humanization of education; formation of systemic thinking; individualization of education; digitalization of the cultural process; continuity;
- processes of innovative development of education, in particular, content, standards, educational and methodological support, methods, means, resources, technologies of education and its management systems;

- digitalization of education, which meets the requirements of the modern information society and involves the creation of a single informational educational space based on computer technologies.

The formation of these factors is determined by such changes in society as: first, high requirements to the professionalism of specialists; second, new individual needs of learners considering their personal development and the process of obtaining high-quality knowledge; third, the implementation of new opportunities for improving the content and learning technologies in the global digitalization of the education system.

Factors and tendencies of the innovative development of Open Education became the subject of scientific interest of Shunevych (2008). He considers that the development of Open Education is caused by political, economic and socio-cultural changes of the country. Regulation of Open Education policy takes place at the government level, taking into account educational requirements of the population. The increasing use of ICT supported by government policy caused the following tendencies toward the development of educational system:

1) establishment of open, virtual and hybrid higher education institutions which use the existing means and methods of Open Education and, additionally, create their own innovations in virtual educational environment. Their educational policy is regulated by government programs with the consideration of the capabilities of educational institutions and the needs of a specific region;

2) launching of open distance courses in the field of economic, social and computer sciences, which are of high demand among the country population;

3) open access of relevant commissions and associations to student evaluation results to obtain appropriate accreditation;

4) implementation of innovative teacher training courses within the framework of open education environment;

5) provide financial support to educational institutions by means of government or grant programs or scholarship funds.

Educational and political approaches to introducing an innovative educational paradigm are considered in the studies of Geits [5]. Scientists declare that in the conditions of innovative technological development of society, knowledge becomes the main vector; therefore, formation of an individual professional potential, which is provided by the education system, should be implemented in the conditions of innovative education. For successful implementation of the innovative development of education system, scientists consider it necessary to take a number of steps:

1. Development of an innovative education system with the student-oriented learning which will contribute to the development of lifelong learning. To implement this task, certain conditions are required: correspondence of domestic education with European standards; granting wider autonomy to universities establishing cooperation between university and industry sectors of science for successful development and implementation of research projects or programs; ensuring high-quality professional training of education staff; implementation of modern ICT in the educational process; attracting foreign students to Ukrainian universities and creating conditions for encouraging talented youth to study under the grant programs or scholarship funds.

2. Correspondence of professional training of education staff with modern innovative development of society. Considering the tasks of the program 'About the Strategy of Sustainable Development 'Ukraine – 2020' scientists believe that successful implementation of social and professional development of society is possible on the basis of innovative development of education system.

3. Increasing of the innovative activity of the population. Much attention is paid to the development of the lifelong learning. An important condition for the implementation of the latter one is the use of Open Education means, in particular, distances learning. Among the measures of effective increase of the innovative activity of the population is the popularization of distance forms as well as increasing of the flexibility of distance education programs with student-oriented approach.

So, within the scope of consideration of the educational and political aspect of the phenomenon the fundamental principles of innovative development of modern education were clarified. They are the following: humanization, democratization, digitalization, openness of education for everyone. The factors and ways of development of Open Education identified by scientists have a complex nature and are conditioned by both the educational, political and socio-cultural needs of society, as well as its economic and technological capabilities.

The formation of Ukrainian information society includes the qualitative modernization of the educational sector, first of all, the introduction of new types of education, in particular Open one. Studying within the Open Education system becomes possible due to the use of the innovative information and communication

technologies, distance learning principles and the obtaining of relevant abilities, skills and competencies.

Thus, the necessity to reform the national higher education system is emphasized in the following government documents: Law of Ukraine 'About Higher Education', 'Education', 'Scientific and Scientific-Technical Activity' [7;8]. The priority areas of the state educational policy are defined as:

1) promoting of the development of lifelong learning;

2) open access to higher education;

3) integration of Ukrainian higher education system into the European one under the condition of keeping and developing of achievements and progressive traditions of the national higher education;

4) government support of teacher training courses within the priority branches of economic activity, areas of fundamental and applied scientific research, scientific and pedagogical activities;

5) government support of educational, scientific and innovative activities of universities, academies, institutes, colleges, in particular, by providing tax, fee and other mandatory payment benefits to higher educational institutions to stimulate such activities;

6) open access to the formation of the structure and scope of educational and professional training of higher education specialists.

The 'National strategy of the development of education in Ukraine for the period until 2021' states the necessity of introduction of Open Education elements into the national educational system. Its main areas are the following:

1) formation and implementation of an informational educational environment into the system of higher and postgraduate education;

2) development of individual modular training programs of different levels of complexity depending on specific needs of learners;

3) creation of an information system supporting of the educational process aimed at the implementation of its main functions (providing training; socialization; internal control over the implementation of educational standards, etc.);

4) support of the educational process by means of information and communication technologies; providing access of educational institutions to global information resources;

5) creation of a network of electronic libraries and digital materials (electronic textbooks, educational encyclopedias, etc.);

6) creation of a distance learning system, including the learners with special educational needs;

7) creation of a system of information and analytical support in the field of management of educational institutions, information and technology support of education monitoring.

The importance of distance learning in higher education system is claimed in the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine 'Regulations on distance learning' [6]. This document outlines the main goals and tasks of distance learning. Thus, its aim is to provide learning by means of modern information and communication technologies within the education and

qualification levels in accordance with state education standards; according to the admission programs, foreigners' training and enhances qualification programs.

The main task of distance learning is to provide citizens with the opportunity to ensure their constitutional right to obtain the education and professional qualifications, improve their qualifications without consideration of their gender, race, nationality, social and property status, type and nature of occupations, worldview beliefs, party affiliation, religion, state of health, place of residence.

The document outlines:

1) the methods of implementing distance learning principles (the use of distance learning form as a separate one as well as in combination with other forms of traditional learning);

2) rules of formation of the educational process according to the distance form of education: forms of the educational process (individual work, class work, practical training, control measures); types of educational classes (lecture, seminar, lesson, practical classes, laboratory classes, consultations and others), which are held remotely in synchronous or asynchronous mode according to the curriculum; kinds of educational materials (video, audio, graphic and text information in synchronous or asynchronous mode);

3) rules of organizing the educational process using distance learning technologies (categories of the population; types of educational activities using ICT; additional distance learning technologies in the system of inclusive and professional education);

4) scientific and methodical support of distance learning with the intention to improve the qualifications

of pedagogical staff in terms of their competencies in the use of distance learning technologies.

Effective modernization of the content and formation structure of higher education is a successful step in implementing the tasks of the government towards the formation of Open Education. The basic component of Open Education is open learning, which is implemented through the distance learning system as the part of the country's education system based on a regulatory and legal principles including technical, logistical and financial support, which implements open learning features within the higher, postgraduate and lifelong education, as well as self-education. Guided by the president's order in the 'Regulations of Distance Learning', distance learning Centers were formed on the bases of higher education institutions which required clear coordination.

We should state that there is a number of state institutions and organizations which deal with the issue of organizing and implementing of Open Education principles into Ukrainian educational system, in particular, the Department of Higher Education of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine; Ukrainian Institute of Information Technologies and Teaching Aids; Institute of Modernization of Education Content; Institute of Educational Analytics of the Ministry of Education and Culture; Coordination Council of the Development of Distance Learning at the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine; Committees of the Coordination Council of the development of the distance learning system; the leading and subordinate (regional, principal, local) Centers of the distance learning system, which provide certain functions (see fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Functions of state institutions and organizations

The leading role in the development of Open Education in the country plays the Ukrainian Institute of Information Technologies and Teaching Aids. Among its main activities are the following: participation in the development of strategic programs and regulatory documents of use of ICT in education; creation of distance courses and distance learning software; support of educational services using ICT and distance learning principles; training of distance learning specialists; certification and expertise in the field of education (on behalf of the Ministry of Education and Culture); conducting marketing research of ICT and distance learning in education; participation in the development of measures to protect copyright and intellectual property objects in the field of ICT in education.

Specialists of the Institute develop training courses and implement projects based on the use of Internet technologies (e-learning) in the field of secondary, higher, postgraduate and self-education.

The purpose of the Institute of Modernization of Education Content is scientific, educational and methodological support of the process of modernization of education content as well as the development and socialization of the learners by means of fundamental and applied scientific research followed by the implementation of their results.

The main goal of the Institute of Educational Analytics is realized through scientific, scientific-organizational, scientific-technical and analytical activities in the following directions:

- analysis of qualitative and quantitative industry indicators;
- regulatory, organizational, scientific-methodical and information support of the educational process;

- innovative activity;
- collection of statistical data of the education system status;
- creation of databases, information and analytical guides in the field of education;
- applied scientific research and experimental developments in the field of Social Sciences and Humanities;
- monitoring of qualitative and quantitative indicators of the status of education development.

The aim of the Coordinating Council's activity is ensuring the coordination of work of the formation and implementation of government policy towards the development of Open Education.

Committees of the Coordination Council are separate organizational branches of the Coordination Council, which provide quality monitoring, expertise and certification procedures of distance learning and ensure it with regulatory and organizational, scientific and methodical, financial and technical support.

The main tasks of the Leading Center of distance learning are the following: developing of regulatory and legal documents of distance learning activity, developing of criteria, tools and quality control systems of distance learning; approbation of new distance learning courses; consulting support of the activities of educational institutions and organizations toward the developing and implementation of distance learning technologies; participation in international cooperation within distance learning activity.

The subordinate (regional) Centers of distance learning are branches of leading educational institutions of III-IV levels of accreditation in regional centers of Ukraine. They provide organizing support within Open Education to other centers of distance learning in

particular region. The aims of their work are: developing of distance courses; provide advanced training of staff enabling them to work in distance learning system; approbation and implementation of innovative methods of organizing of Open Education; provide final examination of distance learners; ensure open access to educational and informational resources of basic and local centers; cooperation with local government bodies in order to meet regional needs in training or upgrading of qualifications of specialists; participation in international cooperation in the field of distance learning.

Principle Centers of distance learning are subordinate branches of leading educational institutions which specialize in one or more fields of training of any branch affiliation within distance learning. The tasks of the Centers are: developing of didactic and methodical support of distance courses; approbation and implementation of distance learning technologies in the basic areas of training; developing of distance courses in the basic areas of training; creation of certified distance courses in certain field(s) of training; participation in international cooperation in the field of distance learning.

Local Centers are the branches of educational institutions which provide distance learning. Local Centers ensure: approbation and implementation of innovative methods and technologies of organizing distance learning; developing of distance courses; participation in international cooperation in the field of distance learning within the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine of 'Regulations on distance learning'.

The organization of Open Education on the basis of universities can be represented by the scheme on figure 2.

Fig.2. Organization of distance learning in universities

Local Centers which are based in higher educational institutions are divided into open and mixed types according to the features of the organizing of

Open Education. Mixed types are the ones which combine traditional and distance form of learning. Nowadays most of higher education institutions in Ukraine are of mixed type.

Thus, the current tendency of innovative transformations of Ukraine into Open Education is the organizing of a national information and communication infrastructure through a series of measures: the creation of government institutions and branches for the formation and implementation of Open Education principles, ICT support of higher education, training of staff to work within Open Education system.

The management of Open Education in Ukraine is provided by the Ministry of Education and Science; the scientific support of innovations ensured by the scientists of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine.

The analysis of methodological and technological foundations of Open Education in Ukrainian universities shows that the most important features of the system are the following: use of technological equipment taking into account the specifics of a particular subject and specialty; formation and implementation of student-oriented learning methods; development of criteria and technologies for ensuring high quality of online learning; support of lifelong professional development of teachers working within Open Education programs.

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